

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2024-25 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Energy Budget Analysis of Earthquake Ruptures at Cascadia

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SUMMARY

The Structural Geology research group in the Geology Department at San José State University (SJSU) built a structural model to generate physics-based, dynamic earthquake ruptures along the Cascadia subduction zone with support from this CRESCENT seed grant. By varying the initial conditions near the megathrust in a series of scenarios by changing the fluid pressure gradient, this work:

1. Quantifies energy budget variations due to loading of the megathrust;
2. Evaluates how earthquake energy budget components vary across subduction zones by comparing Cascadia results with models of the 2004 Sumatra-Andaman earthquake (Madden et al., 2022).

Preliminary key findings include:

- The gradient in pore fluid pressure controls the location of slip, peak slip rate and stress drop along a megathrust across different subduction zones, with implications for tsunami hazard;
- Realistic initial conditions produce ~15 % of total energy radiated as seismic waves while the remaining ~85% is fracture and frictional energy across different subduction zones.

This project aligns with CRESCENT goals to develop a better understanding of Cascadia earthquakes and to train the next-generation of geoscientists. It aligns with priorities 2 and 3 of the Dynamic Rupture, Earthquake Cycle and Tsunamis Group to deepen understanding of dynamic rupture behavior at Cascadia and priority 5 of the Geoscience Education and Inclusion Priorities Group by leveraging achievements from the 2024-25 CRESCENT Twinning Program through continued support of 2024-25 CRESCENT Twinning Mentee Lindsay Gross. This project supported training of a graduate student in numerical modeling and contributed to workforce preparation through a student poster presentation at the 2026 Seismological Society of America Annual Meeting in Pasadena, CA.

BACKGROUND

That energy is not created or destroyed, but can be transformed from one form to another, is a basic law of physics. Large earthquakes are massive energy transformation events. Prior to earthquakes, potential energy is stored in the crust as it strains under the relative motion of tectonic plates locked at their boundaries. During earthquakes, when fault and rock strength is overcome, this potential energy is released and converted into (1) radiated energy of seismic waves, (2) fracture energy associated with activation of the next portion of the fault and off-fault permanent damage, and (3) frictional energy dissipated as heat during sliding (e.g. Abercrombie and Rice, 2005) (Figure 1a). However, earthquakes are complicated physical phenomena that challenge simple accounting of these energy components.

How energy is allotted into each of these categories during an individual earthquake (Figure 1b) is influenced by initial stress conditions, fault geometry, fault strength and co-seismic rupture behavior, but constraining initial rupture conditions and calculating energy partitioning for a real earthquake remains difficult due to the scarcity of comprehensive data. Numerical modeling provides opportunities to control the input parameters and test their influence on energy budget components, compare model earthquakes across different subduction zones, and to compare model estimates with those derived from seismological observations, when and where available. In addition, a realistic energy profile may differentiate a set of non-unique model results that all match other earthquake observations equally well.

No large earthquake has occurred at Cascadia since 1700, before the modern instrumental period. Therefore, this project develops scenario earthquakes across a range of initial conditions. We quantify energy budgets of these scenario ruptures and compare these results with those from both models and observations of the 2004 M9.1 Sumatra-Andaman earthquake (Madden et al., 2022).

The models are run with SeisSol, an open-source computational tool that solves the physics of fault rupture and seismic wave propagation. SeisSol uses an ADER-DG scheme, where ADER refers to the Arbitrarily high-order DERivatives time-stepping procedure and DG refers to the high-order Discontinuous Galerkin finite element method (Pelties et al., 2012). SeisSol is optimized for High Performance Computer (HPC) platforms (Uphoff et al., 2017). SeisSol accommodates non-planar fault geometries and is verified for different on-fault frictional behaviors (Gabriel et al., 2013) and off-fault plasticity (Wolherr et al., 2019). Inputs for SeisSol models include a structural mesh that includes the megathrust interface, material properties around the interface and initial stress on and strength of the interface. Results include the evolution of slip, slip rate, rupture velocity and stress along the fault interface from nucleation to cessation of the modeled earthquake. SeisSol also solves for deformation, stress and strain off the fault and the propagation of seismic waves emitted during fault displacement.

COMPLETED WORK

We initially proposed to use the 3D mesh from Ramos et al. (2022) informed by geodetic locking models by Melgar et al. (2022). However, the publication of quasistatic modeling results for Cascadia by Elston et al. (2025) provided an ideal opportunity to incorporate contrasting megathrust interfaces into the dynamic rupture models. These megathrust geometries, shown in Figure 2a, are from Bloch et al. (2023), McCrory et al. (2012), Sypus and Wang (2024) and Hayes et al. (2018, slab2). This widens the impact of this work by allowing the study to address the influence of fault geometry on rupture dynamics, rather than exploring coupling patterns already studied by Ramos et al. (2021). In the abstract, Elston et al. (2025) recommends these efforts, due to the large differences in fault geometry represented by the four different structural interpretations and the resulting contrasts between quasistatic modeling results. This opens pathways for future analysis of the dynamic rupture modeling results alongside long term behavior.

Taking advantage of these megathrust geometries required developing a new meshing procedure. This was accomplished through collaboration between SJSU graduate student Sean Hsieh and Dr. H. Elston, formerly at Smith College. In addition to the megathrust interface from Bloch et al. (2023), McCrory et al. (2012), Sypus and Wang (2024) or Hayes et al. (2018, slab2), each mesh will include bathymetry data from GEBCO (Figure 2b). Two of the four meshes are complete, and we currently are running scenarios on the mesh with slab2. Results reported here use slab2 geometry (Figure 2c).

We proposed to generate earthquake scenarios across the range of maximum compressive stress orientations along the subduction zone, from 35°, 45° and 60° at latitudes of 42°, 43° and 44° respectively (McKenzie & Furlong, 2021). This rotation results from combined effects of the subduction zone tectonics with transform tectonics to the south (McKenzie & Furlong, 2021). We revised this plan to instead load the fault in each model with the complete, heterogeneous stress field that includes the rotation. The magnitudes of the principal stresses are determined relative to the depth-dependent vertical stress in all scenarios following Madden et al. (2022). We include heterogeneous elastic media surrounding the fault from the Cascadia 3-D Community Velocity Model (Stephenson et al., 2017). We run each scenario with static and dynamic coefficients of friction of 0.3 and 0.1, respectively. These are uniform spatially within each model (Madden et al., 2022). We begin with a linear slip-weakening friction formulation, without complexities such as thermal pressurization or fault healing (Segall and Bradlet,

2012). This produces an energy budget for which the dynamic stress (τ_d) and the final stress (τ_1) are equal (Figure 1b), neglecting healing contribution to the fracture energy (W_r) for now.

For each interface geometry, we run scenarios A and B, which vary in the pore fluid pressure gradient. Scenario A reflects the common approach of increasing pore fluid pressure with depth at a slightly lower rate than the lithostatic gradient. We refer to this as a sublithostatic gradient. This leads to an increase in stress resolved on the megathrust with depth. Scenario B includes a pore fluid pressure that parallels the lithostatic gradient exactly, as supported by theory (Rice, 1992) and observations (Suppe, 2014). We refer to this as a lithostatic gradient. The pore fluid pressure magnitude is assumed to be at 97% of lithostatic pressure, following insights from Madden et al. (2022) supporting overpressured coseismic conditions. The choice of pore fluid pressure gradient is critical for assessing tsunami hazard. In models of the 2004 Sumatra earthquake, fluid pressure mirroring the lithostatic gradient causes slip and peak slip rate to shift toward the trench, increasing tsunami potential (Madden et al., 2022). We find similar results in the Cascadia models (Figure 3c, d). In addition, stress drop is concentrated at depth along the interface in Scenario A, but distributed across the megathrust interface in Scenario B. This was observed in the Sumatra results as well (Madden et al., 2022).

We calculate energy budgets for the Cascadia and Sumatra scenarios as follows and compare them in Table 1. We emphasize that these are preliminary energy budget results. In SeisSol, the total potential energy (W_{total}) is adopted from equation (3) of Ma & Archuleta (2006) where t_f is the total time of the model, Σ is the fault surface, $\Delta\tau$ is the shear stress drop on the fault and $\Delta v(t)$ is the slip velocity:

$$W_{total} = - \int_0^{t_f} \int_{\Sigma} \Delta\tau(t) \cdot \Delta v(t) d\Sigma dt$$

The fault energy (W_{static}) includes both frictional and fracture energy and is adopted from equation (4) of Ma & Archuleta (2006) where $\Delta u(t_f)$ is the final slip:

$$W_{static} = - \int_{\Sigma} \frac{1}{2} \Delta\tau(t_f) \cdot \Delta u(t_f) d\Sigma$$

The radiated energy (E_R) is calculated as the change in work:

$$E_R = W_{total} - W_{static}$$

W_{static} can, in theory, be divided into the frictional and fracture energy components. We calculate rough estimates using the equations in Table 1 (Coffey et al., 2023). Variables are as follows: $\Delta\tau_m$ is mean stress change on the fault, D is mean final slip, D_c is the critical slip weakening distance, μ_d is the dynamic friction coefficient, σ_n is the mean normal stress, and $\tau_d = \mu_d \sigma_n$ is the mean dynamic fault strength. We find that these estimates consistently undershoot the SeisSol calculation. This may be due to an misestimate of fault area or the inadequacy of calculating EF and EG using average, final values.

PRESENTATIONS & NEXT STEPS

Preliminary work was presented by PI Madden at the CRESCENT Spring Virtual Session on 5/21/26. Undergraduate and former Twinning mentee Lindsay Gross presented an early version of this work at the CRESCENT Annual Meeting on 10/29/2025. Lindsay, undergraduate Corey Liscombe and graduate student Sean Hsieh presented the models at the SSA Annual Meeting on 4/16/26. This grant also supported a presentation by PI Madden at the CRESCENT Annual Meeting on 10/29/25 titled “Modeling earthquakes with undergraduate students: challenges & highlights”. In addition to fine tuning the models

to achieve consistency in initial conditions across the four megathrust geometries, energy budget results will be analyzed in more detail. Following completion of this work, we plan to publish this work in JGR-Solid Earth.

Table 1: Preliminary energy budgets results from modeled earthquake ruptures

Model	Seismic moment (N-m)	Mw	Total work (J)	Static work (J) (% of total work)	Radiated energy (J) (% of total work)	EF = $\frac{1}{2}(\Delta\tau_m * D_c)$ (J/m ²) [*fault area (J)]	EG = $\tau_d * D$ (J/m ²) [*fault area (J)]	EF+EG (J)
SumA	3.78E+22	9.0	3.63E+18	3.19E+18 (88 %)	4.44E+17 (12 %)	8.00E+06 [5.04E+17]	1.20E+06 [7.56E+16]	5.80E+17
SumB	4.93E+22	9.1	4.23E+18	3.67E+18 (87 %)	5.60E+17 (13 %)	2.00E+07 [1.26E+18]	1.20E+06 [7.56E+16]	1.34E+18
CascA	8.62E+22	9.2	3.38E+18	2.84E+18 (84 %)	5.39E+17 (16 %)	1.89E+07 [6.79E+17]	9.43E+05 [3.40E+16]	7.13E+17
CascB	1.19E+23	9.3	5.32E+18	4.51E+18 (85 %)	8.15E+17 (15 %)	2.60E+07 [9.37E+17]	1.14E+06 [4.09E+16]	9.78E+17

Figure 1: Schematics of the earthquake energy budget components from (a) Cooke & Madden (2014, Fig.1) and (b) Gabriel et al. (2024, Fig.1). In A, W_{ext} is external work and its change is equal to the sum of frictional energy (W_{fric}), seismic radiated energy (W_{seis}), and propagation energy (W_{prop}), a modified fracture energy. In B, the change in work (ΔW) is equal to the sum of frictional energy (F), seismic energy (E_s), and fracture energy (G), which includes the work of fault restrengthening (W_r).

Figure 2: (a) Dip (top row) and curvature (bottom row) for the McCrory, Slab2, Sypus and Bloch models of the Cascadia megathrust interface. Black lines are 5 km depth contours. (Elston et al., 2025, Fig.2). (b) Cascadia model with bathymetry from GEBCO and (c) the slab2 interface (Hayes et al., 2018) megathrust geometry (shallowing toward upper left corner) combined in an unstructured tetrahedral mesh suitable for numerical simulation with SeisSol. (d) Vertical surface displacement (u_3) during the earthquake rupture (positive up).

Figure 3: Final slip (ASI, m) along the slab2 Cascadia megathrust interface during the rupture in (a) Scenario A and (b) Scenario B. Total stress change (Pa) along the interface during the rupture in (c) Scenario A and (d) Scenario B.

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